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DETERMINANTS OF KNOWLEDGE AND PERCEPTIONS OF BURULI ULCER AMONG HOSPITAL STAFF AND COMMUNITY WORKERS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Buruli ulcer, caused by *Mycobacterium ulcerans*, is a neglected tropical disease associated with disability and stigma. Adequate awareness among both health and non-health workers is vital for early recognition and reduction of misconceptions. The objective was to assess knowledge, attitudes, and predictors of Buruli ulcer awareness among personnel of Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 327 hospital staff recruited through random sampling. Data were obtained using a structured questionnaire covering socio-demographics, knowledge of Buruli ulcer, and attitudinal responses. Knowledge was categorized as good or poor. Associations were analyzed with chi-square and regression models, with significance at $p < 0.05$. Participants' mean age was 41.31 ± 10.50 years; most were female (52.9%) and held tertiary education (97.2%). Health workers comprised 85.3%, mainly nurses (38.2%). Overall, 58.1% demonstrated good knowledge. Among health workers, 59.1% had good knowledge, compared to only 20.8% of non-health workers. Specific knowledge showed that 72.8%

identified *M. ulcerans* as the causative agent, 41.9% recognized culture as the diagnostic gold standard, and 74.2% knew the correct antibiotic regimen and duration. Attitudes varied: 30.9% expressed compassion and willingness to help, 26.3% compassion with avoidance, 30.6% indifference, and 12.2% fear of infection. Professional experience was not associated with knowledge. Predictors of good knowledge included medical discipline, being taught in school, and receiving refresher training. While health workers showed relatively good knowledge, non-health workers displayed significant gaps. Persistent misconceptions and stigma highlight the need for targeted education and stigma-reduction strategies in both groups.

KEYWORDS: Buruli ulcer, determinants, knowledge, perception, hospital staff

INTRODUCTION

Buruli ulcer (BU) is a debilitating, necrotizing skin disease caused by *Mycobacterium ulcerans*, characterized by progressive skin and soft tissue destruction, leading to severe deformities, disability, and psychosocial consequences if untreated (WHO, 2024). As the third most common mycobacterial disease in immunocompetent individuals, after tuberculosis and leprosy, BU is one of the 20 neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) targeted for elimination by 2030 (WHO, 2024). The disease predominantly affects rural, swampy, and agriculturally active regions with poor sanitation and limited healthcare access, with children under 15 years bearing the highest burden (Eddyani et al., 2023). Nigeria, particularly the South-South, South-East, and North-Central zones, including Benue State, remains endemic (Onwuka et al., 2021; InfoNTD, 2025).

Despite its significant morbidity, BU remains under-recognized and deprioritized in many healthcare settings. There is incomplete understanding of its transmission. Though *M. ulcerans* is detected in aquatic environments, no definitive vector has been identified and this fuels misconceptions among health workers and communities, leading to delays in care-seeking (WHO, 2024). Patients often present with advanced lesions requiring prolonged antibiotic therapy, wound care, and sometimes reconstructive surgery, imposing substantial economic burdens on affected families (Gordon et al., 2023; Meka et al., 2025).

Globally, BU control has seen modest progress, with over 1,500 cases reported in 2023 across 14 countries, including Nigeria (WHO, 2024). Recent WHO initiatives, such as the Buruli Ulcer Laboratory Network for Africa, aim to improve diagnostic capacity and early intervention through training and operational research (WHO, 2024). However, the success of these strategies depends on the knowledge, attitudes, and competencies of frontline health personnel and community stakeholders (WHO, 2024).

In Nigeria, significant gaps in BU understanding persist. Community members often attribute the disease to supernatural causes, such as witchcraft or spiritual punishment, rather than bacterial infection (Adeneye et al., 2022; Onwuka et al., 2021). These beliefs, common across sub-Saharan Africa, influence health-seeking behaviours, often directing individuals toward non-orthodox treatment instead of formal health facilities (InfoNTD, 2025). Stigma further exacerbates the problem, with fear of contagion, despite BU not being person-to-person transmissible remaining widespread (Esmail-Onyima et al., 2025). It is reported that, while many express compassion towards affected individuals, a significant proportion endorse avoidance or social distancing, reflecting stigmatization (Nwafor et al., 2019).

Healthcare workers play a pivotal role in BU control as gatekeepers of early diagnosis, treatment, and community education. However, their preparedness is often inadequate. Assessments in Southern Nigeria reveal that only a minority of health workers possess sufficient knowledge of BU aetiology, diagnosis, or treatment protocols (Uzochukwu et al., 2018). Low risk perception, diagnostic uncertainty, and lack of training contribute to under-reporting and missed cases, weakening surveillance systems (Uzochukwu et al., 2018). Additionally, BU receives minimal attention in Nigerian pre-service curricula for doctors,

nurses, and allied health professionals, and opportunities for in-service training on NTDs are limited by resource constraints (Sarfo et al., 2021; Ngo Bisseck et al., 2022).

Non-clinical hospital personnel, such as administrative staff, patient attendants, and cleaners, as well as community health workers, also shape the care environment. Their interactions with patients and families can either reinforce stigma or foster supportive attitudes. Where misconceptions persist among these groups, patients may face discrimination even within healthcare settings, further deterring timely presentation and adherence (Durnez et al., 2020).

Despite Nigeria's endemic status and emerging reports of BU cases in North-Central regions like Benue State (InfoNTD, 2025), there are few empirical data on the determinants of BU knowledge and perceptions among hospital personnel. Most existing Nigerian studies focus on general community awareness or clinical case series, with limited attention to how professional background, education, income, or prior training influence awareness within health institutions (Ukwaja et al., 2021; Adeneye et al., 2022).

Understanding these determinants is essential for designing effective interventions. Recent trials demonstrate that structured training, both during formal education and as in-service refresher courses, significantly improves BU knowledge, reduces stigma, and enhances clinical practices (Ngo Bisseck et al., 2022; Sarfo et al., 2021). Such evidence supports the feasibility of targeted capacity-building in Nigerian settings.

Given the convergence of environmental risk, cultural beliefs, health system gaps, and workforce preparedness in BU-endemic areas like Makurdi, Benue State, an assessment of knowledge and attitudes among all categories of hospital and community personnel is urgently needed. Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess knowledge, attitudes, and predictors of Buruli ulcer awareness among personnel of the Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

- **Study design and setting:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among hospital staff at the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. FMC Makurdi is a tertiary health institution that serves as a major referral centre for Benue State and neighbouring states, providing both clinical and community-oriented health services.
- **Study population:** The study population comprised hospital staff aged 18 years and above, including both health workers and non-health workers. Health workers included doctors, nurses, laboratory scientists, pharmacists, and other allied health professionals, while non-health workers consisted of administrative staff, attendants, security personnel, and other support staff without formal clinical training.
- **Sample size and sampling technique:** A total of 327 participants were recruited for the study. Participants were selected using a simple random sampling technique from staff lists obtained from relevant hospital departments to ensure representativeness of both health and non-health worker categories. Only staff who provided informed consent were included in the study.
- **Sample size calculation:** The sample size for this study was determined using the single population proportion formula for cross-sectional studies. The study's sample size was estimated using the formula: $n = p(1-p)Z^2/D^2$. Where n = sample size; p = prevalence of characteristic of interest which is prevalence of good knowledge (29%) of Buruli ulcer among health-related personnel from another study (Ekeke et al., 2017). Z = standard normal deviate where confidence level is 1.96 at 95%; D = absolute precision or error margin (5%). This yielded sample size of 316. Due to

possibility of incompletely filled questionnaires, 10 % (32) was added and it added up to 348 (327 with complete data were included in the study).

- **Data collection instrument:** Data were collected using a structured, pre-tested, self-administered questionnaire developed based on existing literature on Buruli ulcer and adapted from tools used in similar studies. The questionnaire consisted of three sections: Socio-demographic characteristics (age, sex, marital status, educational level, occupation, place of residence, income, and years of work experience); knowledge of Buruli ulcer, including awareness, cause, transmission, risk factors, symptoms, diagnosis, prevention, and treatment.

Attitudes and perceptions toward individuals affected by Buruli ulcer was also assessed. The questionnaire was reviewed for content validity by experts in public health and infectious diseases and was pre-tested among a subset of hospital staff outside the study population. Necessary modifications were made for clarity and consistency.

- **Knowledge assessment and scoring:** Knowledge of Buruli ulcer was assessed using a structured scoring system developed to reflect the expected differences in baseline knowledge between health workers and non-health workers.
 - **Scoring for non-health workers:** Non-health workers answered 10 knowledge-based questions covering general awareness and basic understanding of Buruli ulcer, including cause, transmission, risk factors, symptoms, prevention, and curability. Each correct response was awarded one point. For multiple-response items, one point was awarded for each correct option selected. The maximum obtainable score for non-health workers was 17 points. Knowledge levels were then categorized as follows: good knowledge: 13–17 points, poor knowledge: 0–12 points
 - **Scoring for health workers:** Health workers responded to the same general knowledge questions as non-health workers, in addition to 11 technical questions assessing clinical knowledge of Buruli ulcer. These included questions on the causative organism (*Mycobacterium ulcerans*), toxin production, incubation period, characteristic ulcer features, lesion classification, diagnostic methods, antibiotic regimen and duration, surgical management, and physiotherapy. Each correct response was awarded one point, resulting in a maximum total score of 28 points. Knowledge levels among health workers were categorized as: good knowledge: 21–28 points, poor knowledge: 0–20 points
- **Data analysis:** Data were entered, cleaned, and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize socio-demographic characteristics and other independent variables. Continuous variables were presented as means with standard deviations for continuous variables. Categorical variables were represented as frequencies with percentages. Associations between knowledge level and independent variables were assessed using chi-square tests. Variables with statistical significance were further analyzed using multivariable logistic regression to identify independent predictors of knowledge of Buruli ulcer. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.
- **Ethical Considerations:** Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity of respondents were strictly maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS/FINDINGS

Findings from this study are presented in tables and figures below;

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants.

Variable	Frequency (n= 327)	Percentage
Age group in years (mean \pm SD= 41.31 \pm 10.50 years)		
Less than 24	12	3.7
25 to 34	83	25.4
35 to 44	94	28.7
45 to 54	85	26.0
Greater than 55	53	16.2
Gender		
Male	154	47.1
Female	173	52.9
Marital status		
Single	102	31.2
Married	169	51.7
Separated/Divorced	33	10.1
Widowed	23	7.0
Educational status		
Primary	4	1.2
Secondary	5	1.5
Tertiary	318	97.2
Occupation		
Lab scientist	12	3.7
Nurse	125	38.2
Pharmacist	37	11.3
Doctor	81	24.8
Others	72	22.0
Ethnicity		
Tiv	198	60.6
Idoma	56	17.1
Igede	24	7.3
Others	49	15.0
Religion		
Christianity	311	95.1
Islam	16	4.9
Health worker status		

Variable	Frequency (n= 327)	Percentage
Age group in years (mean \pm SD= 41.31 \pm 10.50 years)		
Non-health worker	48	14.7
Health worker	279	85.3
Place of residence		
Urban	279	85.3
Rural	48	14.7
Average monthly income		
<30,000	26	8.0
30,000 to 59,999	68	20.8
60,000 to 100,000	136	41.6
>100,000	97	29.7

The mean age of the respondents was 41.31 \pm 10.50 years, predominantly falling within the 35–44 and 45–54 age groups (28.7% and 26.0%, respectively). Most were female (53%), married (52%), and had tertiary education (97%). About 85% were health workers, mainly nurses (38%) and doctors (25%). Most were living in urban areas (85.3%). Most were Tiv (61%), Christian (95%), and earned 60,000–100,000 monthly (42%).

Table 2: Participant’s responses on some information about Buruli ulcer disease

Variable	Frequency (n=327)	Percentage
Have you heard of Buruli ulcer		
Yes	327	100.0
If yes, where did you hear about it?		
Colleagues	60	18.3
Hospital	83	25.4
Neighbours	38	11.6
School	146	44.6
Have you seen a suspected case of Buruli ulcer?		
Yes	201	61.5
No	126	38.5
Have you seen a confirmed case of Buruli ulcer?		
Yes	142	43.4
No	185	56.6
Do you know the cause of Buruli ulcer?		
Bacteria	207	63.3

Variable	Frequency (n=327)	Percentage
Have you heard of Buruli ulcer		
Yes	327	100.0
Virus	32	9.8
Don't know	88	26.9
Buruli cannot be transmitted through contact with infected persons		
Yes	177	54.1
No	129	39.4
Don't know	21	6.4
Buruli is not transmitted through contact with clothes, surfaces, or beddings		
Yes	188	57.5
No	122	37.3
Don't know	17	5.2
Buruli ulcer can be prevented		
Yes	302	92.4
No	25	7.6
Buruli ulcer can be cured		
Yes	281	85.9
No	31	9.5
Don't know	15	4.6
Buruli ulcer is usually painful		
Yes	264	80.7
No	47	14.4
Not sure	16	4.9
Do you think BU is a very serious illness?		
Very serious	224	68.5
Somewhat serious	16	4.9
Not very serious	4	1.2
Don't know	83	25.4

All 327 participants (100%) had heard of Buruli ulcer, primarily through school (44.6%) and hospitals (25.4%). While 61.5% reported seeing a suspected case, only 43.4% had encountered a confirmed case. Most correctly identified bacteria as the cause (63.3%), and strong majorities believed the disease can be prevented (92.4%) and cured (85.9%). However, knowledge gaps persisted: just over half correctly understood that Buruli ulcer is not spread through person-to-person contact (54.1%) or contaminated surfaces (57.5%). Additionally, 80.7% recognized it as usually painful, and 68.5% considered it a very serious illness.

Figure 1: Knowledge status of the respondents

Overall, 58.1% of participants demonstrated good knowledge (Figure 1). Among health workers, 165 (59.1%) had good knowledge while 114 (40.9%) had poor knowledge (pie chart not included). In contrast, only 10 (20.8%) of non-health workers had good knowledge while 38 (79.2%) demonstrated poor knowledge (pie chart not included).

Table 3: Participant’s responses to risk factors, symptoms, treatment, and prevention of Buruli ulcer

Variable (responses)	Frequency (n= total responses)	Percentage
Risk factor for BU		
Farming	231	29.9
Fishing	132	17.1
Contact with swampy areas	241	31.2
Living near dams	135	17.5
Not aware of any risk factor	33	4.3
Total	772	100.0
Symptoms of BU		
Swelling	182	30.4
Ulceration	208	34.8
Discharge	121	20.2
Joint involvement	71	11.9

Variable (responses)	Frequency (n= total responses)	Percentage
Not aware of any symptom	16	2.7
Total	598	100.0
Treatment of BU		
Medications	291	42.1
Wound care	240	34.7
Surgery	160	23.2
Total	691	100.0
Prevention responses		
Avoid contact with affected person(s)	19	6.2
Avoid mud	81	26.5
Clean environment	66	21.6
Don't know	104	33.9
Health education	28	9.2
Vaccination	8	2.6
Total	306	100.0

Participants identified contact with swampy areas (31.2%) and farming (29.9%) as the leading risk factors for Buruli ulcer, though 4.3% were unaware of any risks. Regarding symptoms, ulceration was most recognized (34.8%), followed by swelling (30.4%), with only 2.7% unaware of symptoms. For treatment, medications were the most commonly cited option (42.1%), followed by wound care (34.7%) and surgery (23.2%). Notably, prevention knowledge was limited: 33.9% did not know how to prevent the disease, while others mentioned avoiding mud (26.5%) or maintaining a clean environment (21.6%); a small proportion (6.2%) incorrectly believed avoiding affected persons prevents transmission.

Table 4: Responses to perceptions and attitudes toward Buruli ulcer

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage
How do/would you feel for someone who has or had Buruli ulcer		
Compassion and desire to help	101	30.9
Have compassion but stay away from them	86	26.3
Fear they may infect me	40	12.2
Indifferent	100	30.6
Total	327	100.0
Interaction with persons having BU		

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage
Freely interact with them	134	41.0
Disallow their children from interacting with them	56	17.1
Do not allow them to work or do business	35	10.7
The community mostly do not support them	43	13.1
Other responses**	51	15.6
Total	319	97.6

****Other responses to interactions with persons having BU**

Offer traditional medicine	21	41.2
Help clean wound	9	17.6
Helping hand for domestic chores	8	15.7
Isolate them/ stigmatize	9	17.6
Make them comfortable	4	7.9
Total	51	100.0

About 31% of respondents expressed compassion and willingness to help people with Buruli ulcer, while 30.6% were indifferent and 26.3% felt compassion but kept their distance. Only 41% would freely interact with affected individuals; others would restrict their children's contact (17.1%) or block their work participation (10.7%). Among additional responses, 41% would offer traditional medicine and 18% would isolate or stigmatize them.

Table 5: Responses of healthcare workers to technical details on Buruli ulcer

Variable (responses)	Frequency	Percentage
Were you taught BU in school?		
Yes	145	44.3
No	142	43.4
Have you received refresher training in wound care?		
Yes	73	22.3
No	214	65.4
Is intensified case screening offered in your facility?		
Yes	77	23.5

Variable (responses)	Frequency	Percentage
Were you taught BU in school?		
No	210	64.2
Are there adequate BU diagnostic equipment in your facility?		
Yes	57	17.4
No	230	70.3
Have you ever managed BU?		
Yes	75	22.9
No	212	64.8
If yes, did they follow treatment to the end?		
Yes	63	19.3
No	16	4.9
Cause of Buruli ulcer disease		
Staphylococcus ulcerans	35	10.7
<i>Mycobacterium ulcerans</i>	208	63.6
Not sure	44	13.5
Toxin produced in BUD		
Inawa toxin	20	6.1
Mycolactone	114	34.9
Not sure	153	46.8
The incubation period is 1-9 months		
Yes	171	52.3
No	62	19.0
Not sure	54	16.5
The ulcers have rolled up edges		
Yes	178	54.4
No	55	16.8
Not sure	54	16.5
Pain and local lymphadenopathy suggest secondary infection		
Yes	249	76.1
No	12	3.7
Not sure	26	8.0
Metastatic lesions may spread through vasculature or lymphatics		
Yes	199	60.9
No	55	16.8
Not sure	33	10.1
Category 1 BUD is a single lesion <5cm in diameter		

Variable (responses)	Frequency	Percentage
Were you taught BU in school?		
Yes	194	59.3
No	47	14.4
Not sure	46	14.1
Missing	40	12.2
Gold standard for diagnosis is?		
Direct microscopy	44	13.5
Culture	117	35.8
Histopathology	74	22.6
PCR	40	12.2
Not sure	12	3.7
Correct antibiotic		
Rifampicin and clarithromycin for 8 weeks	207	63.3
Rifampicin and clarithromycin for 4 weeks	34	10.4
Not sure	46	14.1
Surgery can be used for treatment		
Yes	210	64.2
No	51	15.6
Not sure	26	8.0
Physiotherapy can be part of treatment		
Yes	225	68.8
No	32	9.8
Not sure	30	9.2

Few health workers were taught about Buruli ulcer in school (44.3%) or received refresher training (22.3%). Only 23.5% reported case screening and 17.4% had adequate diagnostic equipment. While most correctly identified *Mycobacterium ulcerans* as the cause (63.6%) and the 8-week rifampicin-clarithromycin regimen (63.3%), knowledge gaps persisted, especially regarding the mycolactone toxin (34.9% correct). Awareness of surgery (64.2%) and physiotherapy (68.8%) as treatment options was moderate.

Table 6: Association between knowledge of Buruli ulcer and other variables

Variables	Knowledge status		Test statistic	p value
	Good	Poor		
Age group			13.843	0.008
Less than 24	4 (33.3%)	8 (66.7%)		
25 to 34	47 (56.6%)	36 (43.4%)		

Variables	Knowledge status		Test statistic	p value
	Good	Poor		
35 to 44	60 (63.8%)	34 (36.2%)		
45 to 54	40 (47.1%)	45 (52.9%)		
Greater than 55	39 (73.6%)	14 (26.4%)		
Gender			7.903	0.005
Male	102 (66.2%)	52 (33.8%)		
Female	88 (50.9%)	85 (49.1%)		
Marital Status			21.488	0.000
Single	50 (49.0%)	52 (51.0%)		
Married	101 (59.8%)	68 (40.2%)		
Separated/Divorced	16 (48.5%)	17 (51.5%)		
Widowed	23 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)		
Educational level			9.838	0.007
Primary	4 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)		
Secondary	0 (0.0%)	5 (100.0%)		
Tertiary	186 (58.5%)	132 (41.5%)		
Occupation			50.925	0.000
Laboratory scientists	8 (66.7%)	4 (33.3%)		
Nurses	72 (57.6%)	53 (42.4%)		
Pharmacist	12 (32.4%)	25 (67.6%)		
Doctors	71 (87.7%)	10 (12.3%)		
Others	27 (37.5%)	45 (62.5%)		
Ethnicity			30.845	0.000
Tiv	105 (53.0%)	93 (47.0%)		
Idoma	24 (42.9%)	32 (57.1%)		
Igede	24 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)		
Others	37 (75.5%)	12 (24.5%)		
Religion			1.973	0.160
Christianity	178 (57.2%)	133 (42.8%)		
Islam	12 (75.0%)	4 (25.0%)		
Place of residence			14.180	0.000
Urban	174 (62.4%)	105 (37.6%)		
Rural	16 (33.3%)	32 (66.7%)		
Average monthly income			47.871	0.000
<30,000	4 (15.4%)	22 (84.6%)		
30,000 to 59,999	27 (39.7%)	41 (60.3%)		

Variables	Knowledge status		Test statistic	p value
	Good	Poor		
60,000 to 100,000	104 (76.5%)	32 (23.5%)		
>100,000	55 (56.7%)	42 (43.3%)		
Were you taught BUD in school?			77.511	0.000
Yes	127 (87.6%)	18 (12.4%)		
No	53 (37.3%)	89 (62.7%)		
Have you received refresher training in wound care?			29.012	0.000
Yes	65 (89.0%)	8 (11.0%)		
No	115 (53.7%)	99 (46.3%)		

Knowledge of Buruli ulcer varied significantly by several factors ($p < 0.05$). Doctors demonstrated the highest good knowledge (87.7%), while pharmacists and other occupations had the lowest (32–38%). Urban residents (62.4%) and those earning 60,000–100,000 naira monthly (76.5%) showed better knowledge than rural residents (33.3%) and lower-income groups. Formal education on BUD in school and refresher wound care training were strongly associated with good knowledge (87.6% and 89.0%, respectively). Religion was the only variable not significantly associated with knowledge status ($p = 0.160$).

Table 7: Regression analysis: knowledge scores and years of working.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F Change	Sig. F Change
1	0.002	0.000	-0.004	0.001	0.971

ANOVA Table

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	0.008	1	0.008	0.001	0.971
Residual	1829.073	280	6.532		
Total	1829.082	281			

Regression analysis revealed no significant effect of years of working experience on knowledge scores ($F(1,280) = 0.001, p = .971, R^2 = .000$).

Table 8: Logistic regression model of factors predicting knowledge of Buruli ulcer

Variable	Adjusted odds ratio (aOR)	95% Confidence interval	P value
Less than 24	1		
25 – 34	0.1	0.63 – 1.3534	0.721
35 – 44	1.2		
45 – 54	0.7		
Greater than 55	0.8		
Gender			
Male	1		
Female	0.888	0.205 – 3.935	0.998
Marital status			
Single	1		
Married	54.535	0.000 -	0.998
Separated/Divorced	14.881	0.000 -	0.998
Widowed	65.12	0.000 -	0.998
Educational status			
Primary	1		
Secondary	1.2	0.000 –	0.999
Tertiary	2.3	0.000 -	0.999
Occupation			
Lab scientist	1		
Nurse	89.752	0.000 -	0.999

Pharmacist	14.414	2.385 – 87.117	0.004
Doctor	5.562	0.807 – 38.328	0.081
Others	0.669	0.087 – 5.120	0.698
Place of residence			
Urban	1		
Rural	3.056	0.467 – 20.010	0.244
Average monthly income			
<30,000			
30,000 to 59,999	1		
60,000 to 100,000	2.381	0.357 - 15.881	0.370
>100,000	0.152	0.033 - 0.711	0.017
	0.152	0.044 - 0.533	0.003
Were you taught BUD in school			
Yes	1		
No	0.033	0.011 - 0.102	0.000
Refresher training in wound care			
Yes	1		
No	0.032	0.007 - 0.153	0.000

Only two factors independently predicted good Buruli ulcer knowledge. Health workers taught about BU in school had 30 times higher odds of good knowledge, and those with refresher wound care training had similarly elevated odds. Age, gender, and residence were not significant predictors.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study provides insights into the knowledge and perceptions of Buruli ulcer (BU) among hospital staff at the Federal Medical Centre, Makurdi, Nigeria, a setting within a known BU-endemic region. The findings revealed that, while healthcare workers demonstrate moderate biomedical knowledge of BU, significant gaps persist in both clinical understanding and social attitudes, particularly among non-clinical

personnel. Over half of all respondents exhibited good overall knowledge, driven largely by health workers' accurate identification of *Mycobacterium ulcerans* as the causative agent and their familiarity with the WHO-recommended antibiotic regimen (rifampicin and clarithromycin for 8 weeks). These results align with expectations that clinical training confers foundational disease literacy and mirror findings from Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire, where health professionals consistently outperform lay populations in BU knowledge (Ackumey et al., 2011; Ahorlu et al., 2013).

However, less than half of health workers correctly identified culture as the historical gold standard for diagnosis, a gap that reflects the limited availability of diagnostic tools in Nigeria. This challenge is also documented in Cameroon and Southern Nigeria, where weak diagnostic infrastructure impedes timely case confirmation (Ngo Bisseck et al., 2022; Uzochukwu et al., 2018). Notably, only 12.2% cited PCR, which is now widely regarded as the most sensitive and field-applicable diagnostic method in endemic settings (Gordon et al., 2023), highlighting a disconnect between global guidelines and local practice.

The disparity in knowledge between health and non-health workers calls for concern. While 59.1% of clinical staff demonstrated good knowledge, only 20.8% of non-clinical personnel had good knowledge. This pattern is consistent with community-based studies in Ogun and Imo States, where misconceptions about BU causation (e.g., witchcraft, divine punishment) remain widespread (Adeneye et al., 2022; Onwuka et al., 2021). Given that administrative staff, patient attendants, and community volunteers often serve as frontline interfaces with affected individuals, their knowledge deficits can inadvertently reinforce delays in care-seeking and erode trust in the health system. This gap highlights a systemic omission where, BU education in Nigeria remains narrowly confined to clinical cadres, neglecting the broader community of health service delivery.

Although 57.2% of respondents expressed compassion toward BU patients, this empathy was frequently tempered by avoidance or fear. Some respondents feared infection (12.2%), despite BU being non-contagious, while 30.6% reported indifference, suggesting emotional disengagement or normalization of suffering. These results resonate with earlier Nigerian studies that documented stigma, social avoidance, and attribution of BU to mystical causes, even among educated populations (Nwafor et al., 2019; Esmail-Onyima et al., 2025). The coexistence of compassion and avoidance mirrors what has been termed "benevolent stigma" in a Ghanaian study, where pity does not translate into inclusion (Ackumey et al., 2011). Such attitudes, even when well-intentioned, can isolate patients, discourage disclosure, and perpetuate cycles of silence and delay, directly undermining BU control efforts.

Years of professional experience showed no association with BU knowledge ($R^2 = 0.000$, $p = 0.971$), challenging assumptions that clinical exposure alone builds competence in neglected diseases. This finding highlights a gap in continuing professional development and reinforces global evidence that experience without structured education yields limited gains in NTD literacy (Alferink et al., 2020). In contrast, formal education about BU during schooling and receipt of refresher wound-care training emerged as the strongest independent predictors of good knowledge, suggesting that targeted learning, not passive exposure, drives awareness. This aligns with intervention studies in Cameroon, where brief training modules significantly improved diagnostic accuracy and reduced stigma among health workers (Ngo Bisseck et al., 2022), and supports WHO's call for integrating NTD content into pre-service and in-service training across all health cadres (WHO, 2024).

Socioeconomic factors also played a role. Participants in higher income brackets demonstrated better knowledge, possibly reflecting greater access to information, digital resources, or professional development opportunities. Such finding has been observed for other NTDs across sub-Saharan Africa (Osei et al., 2016). Occupation category was likewise predictive, with clinical roles showing markedly higher

awareness, affirming the protective effect of biomedical education but also revealing the vulnerability of support staff.

Despite these insights, important gaps remain. The persistence of misconceptions about transmission even among health workers, suggests that knowledge alone is insufficient to reshape deep-seated attitudes. Global evidence indicates that effective stigma reduction requires participatory approaches that engage communities, leverage lived experience, and address cultural narratives alongside biomedical facts (Renzaho et al., 2007; Tessema et al., 2022). Furthermore, the exclusion of non-clinical staff from BU education represents a missed opportunity to foster inclusive, stigma-free health environments.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while health workers in Makurdi possess a reasonable baseline understanding of BU, knowledge gaps, attitudinal ambivalence, and the marginalization of non-clinical staff threaten effective disease control. The association between structured education and awareness affirms that capacity building and not mere exposure is important for BU preparedness. As Nigeria advances its NTD roadmap, investing in comprehensive, inclusive education for all health system workers will be essential to reducing disability, curbing stigma, and ensuring that compassion translates into dignified, timely care.

➤ Recommendations

Based on these findings, several recommendations emerge. BU content should be systematically integrated into undergraduate curricula for all health-related disciplines. Refresher training on BU diagnosis, treatment, and stigma reduction should be institutionalized at tertiary facilities in endemic states. Targeted sensitization campaigns for non-clinical personnel and community workers, using culturally resonant messaging should be prioritized. Anti-stigma initiatives should involve affected persons as peer educators, drawing on successful models from leprosy and HIV programs.

➤ Limitations

This study has limitations. Its cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and self-reported attitudes may be influenced by social desirability bias. The setting of a single tertiary hospital, may limit generalizability, though Makurdi's status as a BU-endemic hub enhances relevance.

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